

EXPLORATIONAL STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENT MOBILITY PROGRAM CHALLENGES IN DEALING WITH GLOBAL DIVERSITY AND CHANGE

Dian Islami Prasetyaningrum*, Hafida Ruminar, Aurora Ivana, Putra Irwandi
Faculty of Agriculture, Universitas Brawijaya, Indonesia

**Email: dianislami@ub.ac.id*

ABSTRACT

The many opportunities for students to participate in international learning programs, including the International Student Mobility program, must be put to good use. This opportunity is accompanied by challenges that often become obstacles in the learning process. This study aims to explore the challenges faced by students of the International Student Mobility program, which are divided into five factors, namely: academic barriers, social barriers, cultural barriers, and language barriers. Language barrier), and adaptation strategies (adaptation strategies). Using a qualitative approach, interviews were conducted with five research respondents from students of the Faculty of Agriculture, Brawijaya University Malang, who had the opportunity to participate in the International Student Mobility program in various countries in 2021-2022. Fifteen questions were designed to collect data related to the five variables measured, including academic barriers, social barriers, cultural barriers, language barriers, and adaptation strategies. The data collected was then described and analyzed qualitatively.

KEYWORDS

International Student Mobility, international students, challenges

INTRODUCTION

The opportunities to gain study experience on an international scale and the opening of various international collaboration programs, students have many options to be able to take part in international learning activities, including the Indonesia International Student Mobility (IISMA) and International Credit Transfer programs both organized by DIKTI and internal universities. Of course, this opportunity must be put to good use by agencies by sending several potential students to participate in the selection. Ultimately, they will become grantees or awardees of the international student mobility program. By becoming an awardee of global student mobility, students can carry out studies directly in the destination country, offline and online, because they are still in a pandemic.

Many studies show that international students often face challenges in their study trips in foreign countries. Both from the minor things such as adapting to food, weather changes, financial conditions, and health to cultural differences and the language of instruction used. With various foreign language skills, the challenges faced by each student in adapting to the environment will undoubtedly vary.

It is undeniable that adjusting to a new environment will have quite different impacts for each individual. Related to academic life, international students studying offline/online often face problems adjusting to various things, for example, class schedules with significant differences in time, learning, and teaching styles (Bakhtasova & Kazakov, 2016). A student may face several transitional difficulties from everyday social interaction and cultural adaptation situations.

In the adjustment process, there is a possibility of failure in adapting, which causes several psychological symptoms such as feelings of low self-esteem, confusion, homesickness, loneliness, anxiety, anger, feelings of isolation, loss of identity, insomnia, decreased motivation, loss of focus, and lack of self-confidence (Mahmud et al., 2010). Therefore, knowing the challenges international students face in their studies is very important as one of the efforts to support the smooth implementation of academic studies. The institution should consider this when enrolling students in the international mobility program. There are several previous studies related to the challenges faced by international students. Basri & Talebloo (2015) conducted qualitative research on international students in Malaysia by focusing on the challenges and benefits of multiculturalism. The study results show that the challenges are related to facilities, social environment, education system, finances, and the international programs offered. However, this multicultural condition also provides benefits, including positive views regarding careers and personal self-development for students.

Bakhlasova & Kazakov (2016) also conducted research on the same topic. They conducted a case study regarding the obstacles faced by international students in Russia who experience difficulties in adjusting to the lifestyle and academic environment. The problems faced are divided into three aspects: academic, social, and cultural. The suggestions made in this study are to provide more support to international students both academically and non-academically. Another study was conducted by Mbous et al. (2022) regarding the challenges faced by international students during the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States. Six factors were analyzed, including housing challenges, lifestyle, facing the harmful effects of the pandemic, social support, and university.

The study results show that housing and lifestyle challenges have a direct negative impact on students. Using previous studies as a reference, this study explores the challenges faced by students participating in the International Student Mobility program by examining five essential factors: academic, social, cultural, and language. (language barrier), and adaptation strategies (adaptation strategies). This study's results help add more references for both institutions and potential students who can participate in student exchange activities and international student mobility.

RESEARCH METHODS

Location and Participant of the Research

Participants in this study were students from the Faculty of Agriculture, Brawijaya University, Malang, East Java, Indonesia, who took part in the International Student Mobility program in 2021-2022 in the Indonesian International Student Mobility Awards (IISMA) and International Credit Transfer programs. Five students were selected as respondents and were students in semesters 4-5 at the time of program implementation. Respondents carried out student mobility programs in various countries so that they could provide quite extensive and varied data. Data was collected through in-depth interviews, which were carried out online via the zoom education.

Research Stages

This study used a qualitative approach by conducting in-depth interviews with respondents. A qualitative approach using in-depth interviews was adopted to understand the challenges faced by international students studying in foreign countries. The interview session was conducted online using the zoom education application. Each respondent gets a time allocation of 60 minutes in the interview. The interview will be recorded and transcribed.

The interview questions are related to the experiences of international students while implementing the International Student Mobility program. The questions asked were 15 semi-structured questions to measure variables and explore answers from respondents. The variables measured in this study include academic barriers, social barriers, cultural barriers, language barriers, and adaptation strategies. A list of questions was created as a measurement guideline to support the smooth running of the interview process. Interviews were carried out using the Indonesian language to facilitate the delivery and receipt of information by interviewers and research respondents.

After collecting data and writing transcripts, the data is analyzed and explained based on the variables that have been measured. These variables are categorized into (1) challenges and struggle faced by students in various settings (academic, social, cultural, and language) and (2) strategies adopted to deal with these challenges.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Indonesian International Student Mobility Awards (IISMA), or the Indonesian Student International Mobility Scholarship, is one of the Belmawa Directorate's events that opens opportunities for undergraduate students from tertiary institutions in Indonesia to participate in the learning process at leading universities in the world. It aims to enrich and enhance their knowledge and competence in the concrete world under their interests and ideals. Students of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Brawijaya, have followed it. Many things can be done while studying abroad, including the following, namely:

1. As the perfect first step to pursuing a career.
2. Improving foreign language skills and understanding of diverse cultures.
3. The opportunity to choose majors and fields of diverse knowledge with internationally recognized quality education.
4. Grow and develop personally when adapting to a new world and culture, and finally.
5. Experience and life skills that will be carried along for life.

The participation of IISMA participants is a valuable experience to improve their abilities and competencies on the international stage. However, there were challenges and obstacles for participants in carrying out lectures during the implementation of the IISMA, as follow:

Learning System and lecture activities

The communication built with the lecturers was related to the academic constraints during the implementation, which IISMA students attended. It can be seen with the learning system and lecturers. Based on the results of interviews, that have been found that the interaction between lecturers and students is still minimal. The interactions built by the lecturers did not seem serious, namely only asking questions during the lesson and discussions, which were built lightly. Students expect intensive meetings and solving various problems in depth and comprehensively. Discussions are limited to class, and they cannot contact the relevant lecturers. In addition, the perceived academic obstacle is that some lecturers have unclear language accents when speaking English, so sometimes, I need help understanding what is being conveyed. Regarding lecture information, there were still sudden changes to the schedule and no further coordination. Thus, informants stated that the lectures impressed like international webinars.

Not only with the learning system and lecturers. Another challenge faced is building communication with colleagues in class. Many challenges are met, including that some

international students need to be fluent in English, making socializing difficult. Assignments are generally carried out individually, but some lecturers give group assignments as a final project evaluation. Usually, the team chosen is those with the same ethnicity, so it becomes challenging to do group assignments. Another factor that supports one's academic ability in carrying out studies is the expectations and reputation of parents. Generally, parents support IISMA participants' choice to register in the destination country. Parents give complete trust to carry out lectures optimally and with full responsibility, namely financial support, lecture facilities, and spiritual, constructive motivation.

Foreign Language Proficiency

The difference in social language faced in achieving global competence is one of the challenges in the IISMA program for Overseas Destinations. The challenges seen are the many differences in terms of society and language. Socially, the culture that is built is still individualistic. The individualistic nature makes it difficult for someone to socialize. Not only that, the language barrier is crucial. Only some people use English as an introduction. That has become a common reason for many local speakers need to be more fluent in English because of their mother tongue. But the ability to speak English comes from the willingness to be brave. The right way is to force yourself. Not everything that is forced is terrible. Being forced to speak English will lead to the courage of this courage and ability will arise. This is anticipated by always practicing and respecting the socio-economic conditions of the community. Try to share experiences and listen to friends who have different cultures to understand the culture better so that we can understand each other and avoid misunderstandings in the future.

Culture Shock

Culture shock in the destination country is one of the challenges IISMA students face. They start from changes in existing culture and lifestyle, which sometimes causes frustration, anxiety, and stress, that is quite heavy. However, IISMA participants generally explained that cultural aspects in the destination country caused no obstacles. The difference in hours with Indonesia can be overcome. The culture of being on time, which is always a reference, can be anticipated by attending class on time and building oneself into a more independent person. In connection with existing cultural constraints, it is necessary to conduct research in advance regarding local habits and crocodiles. So that when interacting with the people there, you won't be surprised anymore because you already know and do research first. However, for food, some IISMA participating students have difficulty finding Asian food in general supermarkets. So when buying Asian food, I have to visit a specialty shop that sells Asian food first, and the price is relatively higher than other foods. The way to deal with diversity is by being tolerant, and trying to understand, appreciate, and respect every existing culture.

Regarding the negative stigma aimed at international students in the IISMA program, there was no negative stigma or prejudice against international students. No issue becomes a label for rejecting the existence of IISMA students to study and develop themselves in the destination country.

In responding to all the challenges of implementing IISMA Student Exchange activities, it is necessary to have strategies and adaptive steps to support study readiness in the destination country. There are some of the supports provided by the home country:

Academic Improvement Strategy in Destination Countries

Many things are being done as a strategic step in improving academic skills and abilities in the destination country, namely studying the introductory courses that are given so that it helps in

discussing and building connections with lecturers and students in class. Record all material provided and create structured folders. To better understand the material presented. In addition, by taking notes, I can find out about things that I have understood and those that I have not understood. When you find something you need help understanding, you can immediately ask questions when the discussion session opens. In addition, making structured folders and notes that have been made will minimize the risk of losing important information and material that has been submitted and make it easier when taking exams.

Active discussion, namely interacting with classmates in terms of exchanging existing information and actively asking or answering questions to lecturers who are teaching to practice concentration and understanding of the material that has been given. Support from countries of origin and destination countries related to academic improvement is facilitated, including information, financial, and administrative assistance.

Provision of housing and dormitory facilities and campus activities.

In general, the housing facilities provided by the destination country are based on each of the intended campuses. As in Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, UTM's dormitories are special for international students. The hostel facilities are excellent, and the room conditions are conducive to studying and resting comfortably. Activities on campus are very diverse and not just classes. There are many non-academic activities in the form of excursions from UTM International, which are carried out by inviting other international students.

Provision of supporting facilities in mastering foreign languages

When registering for the IISMA program, the university provides a free TOEFL test through the Barwijaya Language Center (LBC). It is beneficial because before registering for the IISMA program, we are required to attach an English proficiency certificate. Of course, this aims to avoid any communication obstacles when participating in the program. So, in general, administration and filing of files help students prepare for departure.

Provision of counseling services available on campus (Campus Counseling Service)

Supervisory lecturers and destination campuses for student exchange students mainly carry out campus counseling services. Only a few problems were encountered during the program's implementation, so many IISMA participants did not take advantage of counseling services on campus. One of them is that the University of Szeged also provides mentors as media that can be used for counseling.

Participation in Student Organizations (Students' organizations)

Student organizations are a forum for developing skills and competencies while participating in the IISMA program. One of them is an organization at the University of Destination, namely Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. Student organizations on campus are very well organized. At UTM, student organizations that support international students are part of the International Students Society and the Indonesian Student Association for Indonesian students. Both of these organizations are very helpful if students have trouble. The Faculty BEM at the home university is also very good at helping convey the aspirations of students participating in the IISMA program by coordinating socialization in the MBKM group. In addition, at the University of Szeged, you can join several organizations. German Class Organization. Classes are held two times a week that usually tend to be Master's Degrees and also Ph.D. but are welcome for undergraduate programs in interacting and establishing friendships with these international students.

CONCLUSION

The Indonesian International Student Mobility Awards (IISMA), or Indonesian Student International Mobility Scholarship, is one of the Belmawa Directorate's events that opens opportunities for undergraduate students from tertiary institutions in Indonesia to take part in the learning process at leading universities in the world. This program aims to enrich and enhance their knowledge and competence in the concrete world following their interests and ideals. Awardees from international student mobility students can carry out studies directly in the destination country offline and online because it is still in a pandemic condition.

Many things became challenges for the IISMA awardees in participating in the student exchange. These include problems with the academic system, relationships with lecturers and fellow students, cultural and social influences from the local community, access to Asian halal food, foreign language skills, culture shock, and stigma received by international students in destination countries. Realizing convenience and optimal implementation of IISMA activities, adaptability, and provision of facilities are provided by the government of origin in collaboration with the destination campus. It can be seen by the provision of campus housing and dormitory facilities, supporting facilities for increasing foreign language competence, provision of counseling services, and student involvement in participating in destination campus organizations. The convenience achieved is expected to increase knowledge skills, competencies, and global changes.

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